

EDUCATION VERSUS INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL, MEXICO CASE

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EDUCACIÓN VERSUS CAPITAL INTELECTUAL, CASO MÉXICO

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes and reflects on some indicators of nonsense like "enough to know that on one hand the country's Political Constitution enshrines the right to receive a salary range for a living and the other, for those who manage statistics fixing daily wage in a ridiculous amount, which can be compared with the cost of just over six liters of bottled water or a gallon of gasoline, "built on the current model where social and economic strategies are sustained, that should influence education. The proposal builds on what we consider the changes in the Mexican education system should focus on the meaning of work skills, but currently do not impact the performance of the individual as a goal. In Mexico, living in a state of inequality in which there are few, extremely wealthy who have generated their fortunes for favors granted by the rulers and others very poor who receive poverty wages when they work.

Keywords: strategy, education, intellectual capital

RESUMEN

Este trabajo analiza y reflexiona sobre algunos indicadores de contrasentido como por ejemplo "basta saber que por un lado la Constitución Política del país consagra el derecho de percibir un salario que alcance para vivir dignamente y por otro, para los que manejan las estadísticas que fijan el salario diario en una cantidad ridícula, que se puede comparar con el costo de poco más de seis litros de agua embotellada o cinco litros de gasolina", construidos en el modelo actual donde se sustentan las estrategias de carácter social y económico, que debieran incidir en la educación. La propuesta se construye en lo que consideramos como los cambios que en el sistema educativo mexicano deban focalizarse en el sentido de las competencias para el trabajo, pero que en la actualidad no impactan en la realización del individuo como meta. En México se vive un estado de desigualdad en el que existen unos pocos, inmensamente ricos que han generado sus fortunas por favores concedidos por los gobernantes y otros muy pobres, que cuando trabajan reciben sueldos miserables.

Palabras clave: estrategia, educación, capital intelectual

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Negotium

**Revista Científica Electrónica de Ciencias Gerenciales /
Scientific e-journal of Management Sciences**

PPX 200502ZU1950 ISSN: 1856-180 Edited by Fundación Unamuno / Venezuela / REDALYC,
LATINDEX, CLASE, REVENCIT, IN-COM UAB, SERBILUZ / IBT-CCG UNAM, DIALNET, DOAJ,
www.jinfo.lub.lu.se Yokohama National University Library / www.scu.edu.au /
www.ebscokorea.co.kr , Stanford Edu, www.bib.umontreal.ca, Google Scholar, [+++]

Cita / Citation:

Domingo Alarcón Ortiz y Antonio Francisco Díaz García (2013)

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www.revistanegotium.org.ve / núm 24 (año 8) 79 – 85

OVERVIEW

The global economic situation impacts millions of people throughout the educational process and in the short term won't options in the work market. Educational projects, in teaching from the levels Basic to the top, where the investment is sizeable and applied efficiently, demonstrate results that are non-compliant with the indicators of efficiency, effectiveness and relevance, that enable graduates an easy incorporation to the work market, while the factor of competitiveness in the economy collapses in a brutal way.

This paper analyzes a particular case for Mexico, where comparison of an indicator of human development expressed by the potential of the wealth of an individual, in relation to the GDP (gross domestic product) of the country is false, since this is done between two variables of a different kind: the first a variable qualitative type represented by the potential and the second with a quantitative variable represented by the flow of assets so it builds an indicator with a distorted measurement of the participation of an individual or a company in the economy.

Introduction

GDP (gross domestic product), measures the total output of goods and services of final use that the inhabitants of a country with regard to the economy generated in a given period. In counterpart, the wealth of an economy refers to the value of all the resources that it has, including physical assets, human capital and natural resources.

So it is evident that the GDP and the wealth of the economy in any country are related: GDP is not a measure of the wealth of a country, but the potential for the production of goods and services obtained from such wealth.

If you would like to compare the wealth of an individual with the wealth of an economy would emerge the question: how to estimate a country's wealth?

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The wealth of an individual, a company or a country, can be estimated in the same way of how to obtain the value of any asset.

The main assets or resources of any economy are:

- ◆ Human capital (your people), defined as the work and effort of people, as well as their knowledge, skills, abilities, skills and attitudes.
- ◆ Physical capital, including the Monetary liquidity and credit capacity, as well as machinery, equipment, fixed structures, buildings, houses, land, cars, durable goods, etc., and
- ◆ Natural capital, i.e., natural resources, both the renewable and non renewable.

CASE MEXICO

Today in Mexico do not have an educational project that privilege from the basic level to the top indicators of efficiency, effectiveness and relevance, since educational curriculum at each level are not supported on a platform that should highlight two fundamental elements in the learner: their dignity as person and the potential to educate and train your character fundamental elements that should lead the learner to a full human development.

Made countless proposals according to various situations that are live today, but the factor that is not taken into account in all these proposals, is the recognize the dignity of the person, fundamental value in any human development strategy, rather manifests a situation of corruption and perversion of the sense of ethical-moral formation - Office of any company. This is due to the fierce struggle of political parties and unwilling to make decisions to eliminate privileges and sinecures political classes and the trade unions that have badly managed in the sphere of its competence in the country in at least the past forty-two years.

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Methodology

For this work was taken as a reference an exercise carried out in 2005 by a group of researchers in economics ⁽⁷⁾ in which proposes a mathematical estimation model, resulting in the total value of capital (including the types of capital: human, physical and natural) and for Mexico during 2005 was approximately 6.09 billion dollars, (see graph1).

Graph 1

Of this total, 56% corresponded to the value of human capital, 28% to the value of physical capital of enterprises and households and 16% to the value of natural resources.

This estimate shows that the wealth of the nation lies to a greater extent in the human capital of individuals rather than on physical capital of

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enterprises and households and that the natural resources.

In fact, the value of human capital is more than twice the value of physical capital and is greater than the sum of the values of the physical and natural capital.

Therefore, the research group of the seminar of development of policy skills of the graduate in administration of the UNAM, is currently participating in two programs of basic school levels performance evaluation (secondary) and basic (Bachelor) higher, in order to propose a strategy that is inclusive to make in the teaching-learning process, this privilege that in different subjects that compose it and the extracurricular activities that complement the program include education and training of the nature of the learner, so that really have an impact in the educational process and this is manifested in a better school performance.

The strategy proposed is that it be included in the school curricula in a comprehensive manner and in all subjects that the learner course as well as extracurricular activities that they schedule during the courses, is present the development of skills and talents achieving this through the exercise of the virtues throughout the process, this being the natural environment to train and educate the character.

Below is a picture that suggests that exercise in accordance with the physics of the pupil age.

VIRTUES	HUMAN VIRTUES			
	AUSPICIOUS AGE TO EDUCATE THE CHARACTER, THROUGH THE EXERCISE OF THE VIRTUES			
	UP TO 7 YEARS	FROM 8 TO 12 YEARS	FROM 13 TO 15 YEARS	FROM 16 TO 18 YEARS
THEOLOGICAL	LOVE		FAITH	
CARDINAL	WILL	IRASCIBILITY	CONCUPISCIBILIDAD	
RESULT	JUSTICE OBEDIENCE SINCERITY ORDER	FORTRESS PERSEVERANCE INDUSTRIOUSNESS PATIENCE RESPONSIBILITY JUSTICE GENEROSITY	TEMPERANCE MODESTY SOBRIETY SOCIABILITY FRIENDSHIP RESPECT SIMPLICITY PATRIOTISM	

Figure 1

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In order to achieve in the process may have as a result an alignment in the development of the potentialities inherent in the ethical dimension that we have proposed in⁽³⁾ and thereby achieve a better school performance being the learner a change agent ⁽³⁾.

CONCLUSIONS

There is no doubt that any educational project not supported in the rescue of the dignity of the pupil, manifested by the knowledge, attitudes, skills and competences relating to the personal decision of each individual and the full use of their freedom, would leave things as they are and the stages of human development and opportunities would be far from reaching the bulk of the population negatively impacting the individual and national competitiveness factor.

Suffice it to recall that powers ⁽⁵⁾ "behaviors are dominating some people better than others, and that makes them more effective in a particular situation", facilitated or limited by the educational process in which the learner participates. On the other hand the talent is the effort that manifests itself in various forms and factors that clarify the: knowledge, experience, motivation, interests, skills, attitudes, abilities and potentialities.

Both are consequently behaviors ⁽¹¹⁾ resulting from the formation of the character, which decisively influences the performance of the trainee.

Given the importance of the human in modern economies capital, the efforts that the Government offers should focus increasingly on a permanent improvement of the quality of education in Mexico, since for the majority of households human capital continues to be the main asset that is counted and not supported in multiple assistance curricula offered and most of the times are littered with manifestos of corruption elements as well as attitudes clientele toward political parties who also support them.

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